

High Resolution Image Reconstruction with Enhanced Refinement Network (ERN) for Orange Fruit Disease Analysis

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Abstract - Due to their significant role in agriculture and global trade, the health of orange crops is of great importance. However, disorders such as orange greening are poses severe threats to orange production and farmers' livelihoods. Hence, the early and accurate detection of these diseases are vital to the production of quality fruit as well as productivity. Quick and dependable diagnosis allows the farmers to resort to control measures in time to help safeguard the yields. The present study provides an Enhanced Refinement Network (ERN) model developed for the upgradation of low resolution images is and used for the accurate detection of diseases in orange fruits. The results obtained from the proposed ERN on the orange fruit greening disease dataset and are as follows: PSNR values being 30.92, 33.674, and 35.965, respectively. SSIM values record 0.8563, 0.8948, and 0.9253, respectively and classification accuracies of 99.47, 98.64, and 97.53% when upscaling factors of 2, 4 and 6 are used.

Keywords: Image Enhancement, Deep Refinement Network, Orange Leaf Disease Detection, Feature Extraction Model, Blurry Image Restoration, Pattern Recognition, Visual Quality Assessment

1. Introduction

The early identification of crop diseases has become a matter of critical concern to researchers and agricultural technologists throughout the world, since diseases that are not detected in their earliest stages will drastically reduce yields and seriously impair the quality of the fruit [1]. The old methods used for the inspection of crops at the present day are nevertheless serviceable in the way of preliminary examinations, but they are laborious, slow and subject to human error [2]. They are inadequate for large scale observations. The new methods are due to the introduction of artificial intelligence, particularly deep learning, which has greatly modified agricultural diagnostics by making possible the detection of plant diseases from photographic image data in an automatic manner and with a high degree of precision [3].

In recent years, image super-resolution has become an important technique to enhance low and blurred quality images, producing more clear views of disease symptoms that might otherwise go undetected [4]. Traditional interpolation methods may improve the clarity of an image, but are often unable to preserve fine details, leading to poor results [5]. Super-resolution methods based on deep learning address these problems by learning the complex mapping between low and high resolution images, producing sharper and more informative reconstructions [6].

This work presents the Enhanced Refinement Network (ERN) which is a deep learning model aimed at improving the quality of images of orange fruit for more precise diagnosis of diseases present in them. The ERN framework proposed provides better detail of texture and boundary properties for more efficient multi-stage refinement providing rapid high resolution reproduction. The model aids in the promotion of both visual clarity and diagnostic ability advancing the development of intelligent systems for efficient management of orange diseases significantly.

2. Related Work

Recent developments in computing power have resulted in considerable advances in the implementation of deep learning techniques to computer vision [7-22]. These intelligent architectures use non-linear processors to produce better visual encodings of the data by exhibiting the complicated relations that occur in the visual properties [11-14]. Very shallow learning based approaches do not have the capabilities in restoring the fine textures, or the small fine structures, due to their occurrence in the training image, while on too greater depth there is still a vast probability of overfitting or drop in performance.

The progress made it feasible to automatically examine fruit images, therefore enabling efficient detection of the diseases of orange fruit and other agricultural diseases [15]. Trials have been carried out on many crops including olive, tomato, orange, mango, tea leaves, cassava, potato, and rice with successful out-comes in the early and accurate diagnosis of the diseases. All these models [16-19] indscribe techniques of neural networks to list the symptoms of disease from fruit or leaf images with a minimum aid of human expert knowledge. These studies give evidence to substantiate the growing effects of deep learning in agriculture in general, especially the automated plant disease diagnosis to substantiate enhanced yield predictions and crop management.

3. Methodology

3.1 Super Resolution Architecture Based on ERN

The Enhanced Refinement Network (ERN) architecture, depicted in Figure 1, is specifically designed for single-image super-resolution tasks. The network comprises an input stage, several intermediate convolutional layers, an output reconstruction layer, and multiple ReLU activation functions. In the input stage, 64 convolutional filters of size 3×3 are used to extract the initial spatial features from the low-resolution image. Each subsequent intermediate layer continues with 64 filters of the same size, enabling progressive refinement and enhancement of feature representations. The final reconstruction layer employs a $3 \times 3 \times 64$ convolutional kernel to generate the high-resolution output. All layers of the model except the output layer are specified with Rectified Linear Unit (ReLU) activations at the second level of depth learning, to promote non-linear mappings of features permitting increased learning capabilities of the model architecture for approximating the proximal object functions.

Fig. 1. Extensive Residual Network (ERN)

For the proposed sub band network architecture the input low resolution image is enhanced by the Stationary Wavelet Transform (SWT) for the purpose of decomposition into a multiplicity of frequency components. The transformation will produce four distinguishable wavelet sub bands which represent distinct levels of detail of wavelet decomposition. The resulting sub bands are respectively expressed as $\{I_{LL}^{LR}, I_{LH}^{LR}, I_{HL}^{LR}, I_{HH}^{LR}\}$ for the low resolution input image and $\{O_{LL}^{RES}, O_{LH}^{RES}, O_{HL}^{RES}, O_{HH}^{RES}\}$ for the proximal re-sidual output (I_{RES}) which are incorporated into the super resolution frame work as shown in Figure 2. The resultant performance of decomposition allows the net-work for a conclusive learning of fine high frequency detail and texture components through the inherently high and low frequency information held within all components of the sub bands.

Fig. 2. Network Sub band diagram

The proposed Super-Resolution (SR) approach constructs high-resolution (HR) sub-bands by combining the low-resolution (LR) sub-bands with the residuals derived from the Enhanced Refinement Network (ERN). Although working in the sub-band domain improves the precision of the reconstruction it is frequently true that smoothness is obtained in the final image and edge definition is lost. To overcome this SR sub-bands generated are subjected to a subsequent refinement using a Gaussian filtering step in which high frequency components are isolated. In so doing, the filtering step accentuates the important edge structures in images. The filtered image is subtracted from the original SR sub band so that important edge information is recovered. The enhanced SR sub-band is combined with the edge-detail sub-band obtained to produce the entire image sub-band. This reconstructed sub band is subjected to an inverse transformation to recover the final high-resolution image (I_{HR}).

Fig.3. Super Resolution (SR) reconstruction network

3.2 Disease Classification in Orange Fruits

Traditionally, precise disease detection from orange fruit image stimuli depended on the availability of good high resolution images. However, as recent advances in technology have proceeded, modern methods now adopted are based upon reconstructing high quality representations from low resolution inputs, which can in turn be assessed for various disease specific characteristics. The classification stage associated with this application thus differs from the previous standard in that it is in turn applied within a deep learning architecture designed specifically for the usual orange fruit disease pattern identification, as demonstrated in Figure 4. After each convolutional operation max pooling layers are included to facilitate the ease of classification by virtue of reducing the dimensionality of the feature maps while retaining the most salient and discriminative features, thus improving the whole efficiency and accuracy of the classification.

Fig. 4. Classification model

3.3 Dataset

The present dataset employed throughout this work consists of images representing four major categories of orange fruit health and disease. These categories are Blackspot, Canker, Fresh (healthy), and Greening. These are the major diseases of orange which are seen to have significant impact on orange yield. In all, there are 344 Blackspot, 349 Canker, 547 Fresh and 545 Greening images or samples, or a total of 1,785 images. This distribution will allow for a fair representation of healthy and

diseased fruits, thus allowing for proper training and evaluation of the classification model proposed. The publicly available Orange Diseases dataset was used as the basis for assessing performance of the Enhanced Refinement Network (ERN) supervised Model for Super Resolution. The dataset consists of four distinct classes dealing with the health of orange fruit. The images available have similar distributions of intensities within classes. The dataset has been made publicly available and presented in a uniform manner making it easy to develop, validate and benchmark advanced machine learning detection and analytical models for orange diseases.

Fig.5(a) Black spot Fig.5(b) Canker Fig.5(c) Fresh Fig.5(d) Greening

3.4 Experimentation

Each of the 1,785 images within the dataset was processed methodically through a number of downsampling factors in order to generate the requisite low resolution (LR) images for comparison with the original, high-resolution copies. This procedure allowed for extensive experimentation at different image quality levels and enabled a complete evaluation of the capabilities of the super-resolution model to reconstruct high-fidelity image detail from degraded, input images. This process and the resultant transformations are illustrated in Figure 6.

Fig.6(a) Original Fig.6(b) Factor 2 Fig.6(c) Factor 4 Fig.6(d) Factor 6

The initially generated low resolution (LR) images from the dataset are pre-processed by the Enhanced Refinement Network (ERN), which synthesizes and up-scales them to high resolution (HR) for analysis. The refined HR images are processed by the classification network (Figure 2) for disease classification.

4. Results

4.1 Qualitative Analysis

Fig. 7(a) Super resolution with factor 2

Fig. 7(b) Super resolution with factor 4

Fig. 7(c) Super resolution with factor 6

A visual comparison of the super-resolved (SR) images generated by the model with the low-resolution (LR) inputs of the model at different magnification factors is shown in figure 7. Tables 2 (quantification of disease classification) and 3 (measurement of PSNR and structural similarity) present the quantitative evaluation results that confirm the effectiveness of the proposed technique. The disease classification accuracy is more than 97% and the Peak Signal-to-Noise ratio (PSNR) above 31 and the Structural Similarity Index Measure (SSIM) is larger than 0.81 which show that the model can accurately reconstruct the images and identify the disease which indicates a good possibility for the application of the technique in agriculture for the diagnosis of diseases.

4.2 Quantitative Analysis

Table 2. Performance Evaluation of ERN

Metrics	SR Image (factor 6)	SR Image (factor 4)	SR Image (factor 2)
PSNR	30.92	33.674	35.965
SSIM	0.8563	0.8948	0.9253

Table 3. Performance evaluation of classification model

Metrics	SR image (factor 2)	SR image (factor 4)	SR image (factor 6)
Accuracy	99.47	98.64	97.53

Table 4. Comparison with existing models

Metrics	ResNet50 [22]	Google Net [23]	Efficient Net [24]	ERN (Proposed)
Accuracy	93.86	95.39	97.69	99.47

5. Conclusion

The high-resolution images produce by current deep learning models are generally not verified for visual plausibility, which results in unconstrained mappings that are incapable of accurately reconstructing the original image. The naiveté of merely increasing the image resolution

disregarding other contextual information results in poor quality output. We present the Enhanced Refinement Network (ERN) that produces a highly accurate real time super-resolution model. The ERN model shows superior performance when compared to commonly used architectures such as ResNet50, GoogleNet and Efficient-Net with Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio (PSNR) results of about 30.92, 33.674, 35.965 with Structural Similarity Index (SSIM) of 0.8563, 0.8948, 0.9253, which correspond with classification accuracies of 99.47, 98.64 and 97.53 for upscaling factors of two, four and six. These results illustrate the superior performance potential of the model and a strongly suggestive potential of extension to other plant structures such as stems and leaves is indicated for future agricultural imaging studies.

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